

Statistical Analysis of the Influence of Psychological Well-Being on Teacher Performance at Al-Izhar High School, Jakarta - Indonesia

Fauziah Farhan Yusuf*¹, Ghozali¹, Ilham Nur Elfarhani²

Middle East and Islamic Postgraduate Program, School of Strategic & Global Studies, Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta¹
Teaching and Tarbiyah Faculty Postgraduate, Universitas Islam Negeri Sunan Gunung Djati, Bandung²

Corresponding Author: Fauziah Farhan Yusuf*

Middle East and Islamic Postgraduate Program
School of Strategic & Global Studies, Universitas Indonesia

Abstract:- In the context of secondary education, the role of the teacher is the main axis that determines the quality of learning. Work motivation is one of the driving forces that underlies teachers' desire to provide the best for students and the institutions where they teach. Meanwhile, psychological well-being includes emotional balance and happiness, which will not only influence personal aspects, but also potentially how teachers interact with students in the classroom. This research seeks to explore how the level of motivation and psychological well-being of teachers influences teacher performance. This background provides a basis for understanding that efforts to improve the quality of education must not only focus on teaching methods alone, but also on the psychological and motivational factors that form the core of a teacher's success in the secondary education environment. This research uses quantitative methods. The measuring instrument used in this research is *Teachers' Performance Job Self-Rating Question (TPJSQ)* and *Psychological Well-Being Scales (PWBS)* is developed by Ryff H. The results of this research show that work motivation and psychological well-being have a relationship with teacher performance scores $r = 0.191$ ($p < 0.01$). It means that the higher the psychological well-being score, the higher the teacher performance score.

Keywords:- *Perfomance, Psychological Well-Being, Human Development.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the world of education, teachers are one element that plays an important and crucial role in the teaching and learning process in schools. Teachers become a bridge between science and students to gain a complete, good and accurate understanding. Teachers carry out the main duties and functions of teachers leading the teaching and learning process in the classroom (Suhar Saputera, 2013). Therefore, it is important to pay attention to the good and bad of teacher performance in order to achieve a quality educational system and maintain quality at every level. Researchers have demonstrated significant increases in social and economic value resulting from high-quality teachers (Chetty, Friedman,

and Rockoff 2014; Jackson, Rockoff, and Staiger 2014). Other research finds that teacher performance has a less significant impact on student achievement (Azkiyah, et al., 2014; Sirait, 2016).

According to Law no. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, Articles 1-5 teachers are required to have expertise, skills and abilities that meet certain quality standards or norms and require professional education and act as learning agents whose function is to improve the quality of national education. However, UNESCO data (2016) reports that the quality of education in Indonesia is ranked 10th out of 14 developing countries and the quality of teachers is ranked 14th out of 14 developing countries, based on the Global Education Monitoring (GEM) assessment. This data is an indication of the low quality and quality of education in Indonesia. Apart from that, the performance of teachers in Indonesia is in a worrying position because they occupy the lowest position of 14 countries. Good teacher performance will have an impact on increasing motivation, achievement and the quality of learning in schools. Meanwhile, poor teacher performance can have an impact on the low quality and quality of learning and at worst it can damage students' confidence and self-concept (Koedel et al., 2018).

Psychological factors that influence teacher performance include work motivation. The need to address low teacher motivation stems from teacher shortages reported by many western countries including the US, Australia and several other European countries such as the UK, Germany and Norway (Kyriacou, & Kunc, 2007). Research interest focused on teacher motivation to teach and remain in teaching in the last decade has highlighted possible causes of teacher shortages related to intrinsic and extrinsic teacher motivation, including the aging of the teacher workforce, an imbalance between high demands and lower salaries, limited career opportunities, and lack of job security (Richardson & Watt, 2006; Sinclair, Dowson, & Mc Inerney, 2006; Watt & Richardson, 2007; Watt et al., 2012). The importance of teacher motivation research is also self-evident because it is an important factor that is closely related to a number of variables in education such as student motivation, teaching practices and the fulfilment of

teachers' psychological well-being. Therefore, it is very interesting for researchers to examine this motivation variable.

Mitchell (1978) explains that a person's performance is the added result of motivation and ability. This means that performance will be good if a teacher has adequate abilities and there is ideal motivation to encourage him to achieve his goals. Other research also states that work motivation is important for improving performance in teaching, work motivation is related to well-being in the classroom, good learning, and high motivation of students. Teacher motivation is strictly related to perceptions of self-efficacy in the teaching and learning process (Rochmawati & Nurcholis, 2019). Research in several schools in Indonesia, such as in Lombok and Pekalongan, also shows a positive and significant influence between work motivation and teacher performance (Riyadi & Mulyapradana, 2017; Mimbar, Israwati, & Kartini, 2018). Other research finds that the intrinsic motivation variable has a negative effect on teacher performance (Abos et al., 2018).

Another psychological factor that influences teacher performance is psychological well-being. Research on psychological well-being of teaching staff has attracted the attention of several researchers. This interest stems from the fact that psychological well-being in the world of education functions for the development of a teacher's mental health and professionalism in improving the quality of education. Psychological well-being is seen in several studies as a concept that characterizes the quality of life at work, and this can be seen as a major determinant of productivity at the individual, environmental and societal levels (Noviantoro & Saloom, 2019).

Psychological well-being of teachers is an important factor in improving teacher performance. In practice, psychological well-being has an influence in various fields, one of which is teacher learning activities. Understanding psychological well-being in teachers in carrying out their duties aims to change individuals (teachers) for the better (Fanani & Riyadi 2014). Fanani, & Riyadi (2014) also stated that psychological well-being has a significant and positive effect on teacher performance. The results of this research mean that teacher psychological well-being has a significant direct impact on teacher performance. This research explains that the better the teacher's level of psychological well-being, the more the teacher's performance will improve. Psychological well-being has a positive correlation with the level of performance at work. This means that the higher the level of psychological well-being a teacher has, the better his teaching performance will be. This is related to Briner and Dewberry's (2007) research on teachers in primary and secondary schools in England, the results of which stated that teacher welfare influences teacher performance (Briner & Dewberry, 2007).

Teachers employed in various countries experience high levels of work-related stress and it is reported that approximately 30% of teachers leave the teaching profession due to stress (Chan, 2006; Johnson et al., 2005). A number of studies on mental health among teachers, to date, have focused

on psychological well-being, stress levels, and burnout (Fleming, Mackrain, & LeBuffe, 2013; Maslach & Leiter, 2008). High levels of stress and fatigue not only threaten teachers' physical health but also teachers' self-confidence and self-esteem which ultimately reduces performance (Eatough, Way, & Chang, 2012). In addition, high levels of stress and burnout among teachers cause feelings of dissatisfaction with work which results in a decline in teachers' professional performance (Burke, Greenglass, & Schwarzer, 1996). Apart from that, it disrupts the relationship between teachers and students, and influences students' low academic achievement (Fleming et al., 2013; Spilt, Koomen, & Thijs, 2011), and in general teachers and students suffer psychologically which affects teacher performance and achievement. students (McGrath & Huntington, 2007). In addition, the level of stress among teachers and the inability to cope with this stress negatively affects the level of psychological well-being of teachers (Roffey, 2012; Vesely, Saklofske, & Nordstokke, 2014).

The main implication of these findings is that if you want to improve teacher performance, you need to start paying attention to teacher welfare. How teachers feel every day tends to influence teacher performance and also influences the performance of the students the teacher teaches. This can happen in several ways. For example, happier and more motivated teachers can make students feel happier, more motivated, and more confident. Happier teachers can also concentrate better on their teaching work, and have more motivation to help students who need special attention.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

➤ *Definition of Teacher Performance*

Peretomode (1996) states that teacher performance is a set of obligations and tasks carried out by teaching staff within a certain period of time in an educational setting to achieve learning goals. Peretomode (1996) added that performance is determined by the level of teacher participation in carrying out their daily obligations. Rachmawati (2013) states that teacher performance is the teacher's ability and efforts to carry out learning tasks as well as possible in learning. Performance is said to be good and satisfactory if the goals achieved are in accordance with predetermined standards. Briefly, these four competencies can be explained as follows: pedagogical competence, competence, personality, social competence and professional competence.

Risma (2015) stated that teacher performance is the implementation of the functions required of a teacher. Performance is an act, an achievement, or what someone shows through real skills. Risma (2015) further stated that performance is the result or output of a process. Performance can be interpreted as work performance, work implementation, work achievements, work results or performance.

Ahmadiansyah (2016) defines teacher performance as the product produced by a teacher based on the tasks carried out by him/her in terms of quality and quantity. Teacher performance is the work performed by a teacher in a comprehensive and thorough manner with standards set based

on local regulations. Furthermore, the teacher's ability to carry out his duties as a teacher in the context of coaching students based on skills and abilities to achieve learning goals. Teacher performance in this research is a set of obligations and tasks carried out by teaching staff within a certain period of time in an educational setting to achieve learning goals, as theorized by Peretemode (1996).

➤ *Definition Psychological well-being*

Psychological well-being is a concept that characterizes the quality of life at work, and it can be seen as a major determinant of productivity at the individual, environmental and societal levels (Diener et al., 1999). Psychological well-being is a person's perception of their life experiences based on social relationships and spiritual experiences so that a condition emerges in the form of a positive mood which influences health, success and life satisfaction resulting in an increase in religiosity and a good attitude to life (Diener, 2009).

Psychological well-being developed by Ryff (1989) came from his concern that physical health was not only a measure of someone's happiness but was also marked by someone's psychological well-being. Ryff (1989) states that a person who is psychologically healthy can be characterized by the individual being free from anxiety, negative emotions, achieving their life goals, etc. Ryff (1989) constructs the theory *psychological well-being* itself is based on a combination of several clinical, developmental and mental health psychology theories.

Ryff (1989) define *psychological well-being* with the definition of a condition where an individual can recognize and be at peace with the aspects that exist within himself, can establish good relationships with other people, can be independent and independent in managing various positive and negative matters of his life, able to adapt skillfully to the environment in which he lives. , have a clear, structured and carefully calculated direction and purpose in life and can become a person who grows and develops with the potential he has. Based on the description above, in this study, researchers used definitions *psychological well-being* according to Ryff (1989).

III. METHODOLOGY

This research method uses a quantitative model with a data analysis method, namely regression analysis to determine the relationship between the two variables. This regression analysis technique is used to determine the accuracy of predictions and is shown to determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables (*independent variable*) that is *psychological well-being* on teacher performance (*dependent variable*). The respondents in this research were teachers at high schools in Jakarta with a sample size of 53 teachers. In determining the sample size, researchers refer to determining the number of samples from a certain population developed by Isaac and Michael (1981) with an error rate of 5%. The sample size used was 210 people. In this research, researchers used techniques *non probability sampling* which means the probability that members of the population will be

sampled is unknown. Technique *nonprobability sampling* that researchers use is *accidental sampling*.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Data Normality Test*

The normality test was carried out using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test with the standard that the data tested was called normal if the significance was above 0.05. The following are the normality test results that have been obtained.

1 Table normality test

Descriptives

Descriptives	Perfomance	Psychologycal Well-Being
N	64	64
Missing	0	0
Mean	61.6	77.3
Median	62.0	77.5
Minimum	44	55
Maximum	73	97
Shapiro-Wilk W	0.971	0.991
Shapiro-Wilk p	0.132	0.938

The table above shows the information that the normality test uses Kolmogorov Smirnov obtained for the performance variable has a significant score of 0.132 ($p > 0.05$) and Psychological well-being has a score of 0.938 ($p > 0.05$) which indicates that the data distribution obtained meets the assumption of normality.

➤ *Correlation Test*

The following are the results of the correlation test to determine the relationship between psychological well-being and teacher performance. The analysis used uses the *Pearson's correlation test technique*.

2 Table of Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix		Perfomance	Psychologycal Well-Being
Perfomance	Pearson's r	—	—
	df	—	—
	p-value	—	—
	95% CI Upper	—	—
	95% CI Lower	—	—
	N	—	—
Psychologycal Well-Being	Pearson's r	0.191	—
	df	62	—
	p-value	0.130	—
	95% CI Upper	0.417	—
	95% CI Lower	-0.057	—
	N	64	—

Note. * p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Based on the information contained in the table above, it can be interpreted that there is a significant positive correlation between the psychological well-being variable and teacher performance with $r = 0.191$ ($p < 0.01$). Thus, it can be interpreted that the higher the psychological well-being score, the higher the teacher performance score.

➤ *Linear Regression Test*

Furthermore, to strengthen the results above, researchers conducted a linear regression test to determine the relationship between psychological well-being and teacher performance. The analysis used uses the Pearson's correlation test technique.

3 *Table of Linear Regression*

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²
1	0.191	0.0366

Model Coefficients - Performance

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	51.261	6.7830	7.56	<.001
Psychological Well-Being	0.134	0.0873	1.53	0.130

Data Summary

Cook's Distance

Mean	Median	SD	Range	
			Min	Max
0.0174	0.00718	0.0352	3.94e-7	0.216

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V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this research is that psychological well-being has a significant influence on teacher performance with scores $r = 0.191$ ($p < 0.01$). Teachers who feel good psychologically tend to show better performance in teaching and interacting with students. Therefore, attention to teachers' psychological well-being, both material and non-material, needs to be paid attention to in efforts to improve the quality of education. As a suggestion, it is recommended that educational institutions and the government provide support and programs that support teachers' psychological well-being, such as stress management training, social support, and mental health programs. This can contribute positively to the quality of teaching and learning in educational settings.

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